

Derivation of Cross-Sectional Properties of a Two-Layered 3D Composite Beam Element with Partial Connection

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ABSTRACT

The determination of the cross-sectional properties of the composite beam are of great importance, specifically for estimating the capacity of the structure under general loading conditions. In fact, the torsional rigidity of the composite beam is a crucial factor, particularly, when performing verification against lateral torsional buckling. Using a 3D finite element approach, the authors aim to further investigate this matter and develop simplified expressions for estimating torsional properties of the composite section, taking into consideration the influence of the interlayer connection. Additionally, an expression for computing the effective bending stiffness is proposed.

Keywords: inter-layer slip, effective torsional rigidity, effective warping constant, effective bending stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite structures represent one of the most efficient structural solutions that have revolutionized the way engineers conceptualize construction and the utilization of construction materials based on their respective strengths and weaknesses. To design any composite structure, it is essential to understand the composite action that characterizes the level of connection among its structural components. In the literature, one can find various formulas for computing the effective rigidities for composite beams. For instance, Birsan et al. (1) proposed analytical expressions for computing the effective bending, torsional and shear rigidities for multi-layered composite beams. They adopted the theory of directed curves which was first introduced by Zhilin in (2) and (3). Furthermore, Jean-Jacques Barrau et al. (4), investigated the influence of the cross-sectional warping when developing an analytical expression of the torsional stiffness for an arbitrary composite section with N cylindrical phases. However, there have been limited attempts to integrate the influence of the inter-layer slip when determining the properties of composite sections. To bridge this gap, a 3D finite element approach will be utilized to develop expressions that account for the existence of inter-layer slip in two directions: longitudinal slip and a transversal one. The advantage of this approach lies in its independence from any specific load configurations or boundary conditions. Apart from torsional rigidities, the authors intend to propose an alternative expression for calculating the effective bending stiffness of the composite beam, similar to the well-known gamma method in Eurocode 5. This paper will be organized as follows. In section 2, the composite beam kinematics are described and the model assumptions are presented. In section 3, we establish the equilibrium condition of the composite beam using the principle of virtual work. The linear cross-section constitutive laws are recalled in section 4. Section 5 introduces the displacement-based formulation to derive the element stiffness matrix. In section 6, the cross-sectional properties of the composite section are derived. Sample examples will be presented in section 7 to verify the performance of the proposed expressions. Finally, conclusions are drawn in section 8.

2 BEAM KINEMATICS

2.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions are made for the development of the present composite beam formulation:

1. Each layer of the composite beam is homogeneous and isotropic;
2. The cross-section of each layer remains rigid in its own plane;
3. The vertical separation between the two layers is ignored;
4. The deformation and rotations are assumed to be small;
5. The composite section is symmetric with respect to the y -axis;
6. The two layers are connected by a single row of connectors placed the axis of symmetry of the composite-section;
7. The axial displacement due to torsion (warping effect) is proportional to the twist angle gradient (Vlasov theory);
8. The warping of each layer has no contribution to the stress resultants at any cross-section.

Fig. 1. The composite beam cross-section

2.2 Displacement field

To define the displacement fields of the composite beam, the traditional 3D beam kinematics introduced in the reference (5), is adopted for each layer. Therefore, the displacement fields can be expressed as:

$$u^k = u_0^k - y^k \theta_z^k + z^k \theta_y^k + \omega^k \theta_{x,x}^k \quad (1)$$

$$v^k = v_c^k - z^k \theta_x^k \quad (2)$$

$$w^k = w_c^k + (y^k - c_y^k) \theta_x^k \quad (3)$$

Where:

- (u^k, v^k, w^k) are the displacement fields of the beam (k), with respect to the x -, y - and z -axis;
- u_0^k is the axial displacement of the beam (k) at its cross-section centroid;
- (v_c^k, w_c^k) are the lateral displacements of beam (k) at its shear centre;
- c_y^k is the y -coordinate of the shear centre of the beam (k)'s cross-section;
- $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\theta_x^k, \theta_y^k, \theta_z^k\}^T$ represents the 3D rotation vector about the shear centre of the cross-section of the beam (k);
- ω^k is the warping function of the beam (k) with respect to its corresponding shear centre.

It is worth mentioning that the introduced kinematics is formulated in two distinct reference bases attached to the centroid of each cross-section.

2.3 Slip at the interface

The inter-layer slip is considered in both directions: a longitudinal slip in the x -axis of the beam and a lateral slip in the z -axis direction due to the transverse plane deformation of the composite beam. For a single row of connectors (p), located at z_p with respect to the reference axis of the beam (a) (see *Fig. 1*), the slip is defined as:

$$s_{px} = u^a(x, h^a, z_p) - u^b(x, -h^b, z_p) \quad (4)$$

$$s_{py} = v^a(x, h^a, z_p) - v^b(x, -h^b, z_p) \quad (5)$$

$$s_{pz} = w^a(x, h^a, z_p) - w^b(x, -h^b, z_p) \quad (6)$$

where (s_{px}, s_{py}, s_{pz}) are the three components of the interface slip. By inserting *Eqs. (1), (2) and (3)* into *Eqs. (4), (5) and (6)*, we can express the following:

$$s_{px} = -\Delta u_0 - h^a \theta_z^a - h^b \theta_z^b - z_p \Delta \theta_y + \omega_p^a \theta_x^a - \omega_p^b \theta_x^b \quad (7)$$

$$s_{py} = -\Delta v_c + z_p \Delta \theta_x \quad (8)$$

$$s_{pz} = -\Delta w_c + h^a \theta_x^a + h^b \theta_x^b - c_y^a \theta_x^a + c_y^b \theta_x^b \quad (9)$$

with $\Delta(\cdot) = (\cdot)^b - (\cdot)^a$, $\omega_p^a = \omega^a(h^a - c_y^a, z_p)$ and $\omega_p^b = \omega^b(-h^b - c_y^a, z_p)$.

The no-separation condition (3) imposes that:

$$s_{py} = -\Delta v_c + z_p \Delta \theta_x = 0 \quad (10)$$

The *Eq. (4)* holds true for every connector position z_p , thus:

$$-\Delta v_c = 0; \Delta \theta_x = 0 \quad (11)$$

Therefore, both beams exhibit the same vertical displacement ($v_c^a = v_c^b = v_c$) and the same twist angle ($\theta_z^a = \theta_z^b = \theta_z$). Consequently, the composite beam kinematics can be simplified to the following:

$$u^k = u_0^k - y^k \theta_z + z^k \theta_y + \omega^k \theta_{x,x} \quad (12)$$

$$v^k = v_c - z^k \theta_x \quad (13)$$

$$w^k = w_c^k + (y^k - c_y^k) \theta_x \quad (14)$$

with $\theta_z^a = \theta_z^b = \theta_z = v_{c,x}$. Taking into account the constraints given in the *Eqs. (11), (12), (13) and (14)*, the slip components can be evaluated as follows:

$$s_{px} = -\Delta u_0 - h \theta_z - z_p \Delta \theta_y + \omega_p \theta_x \quad (15)$$

$$s_{pz} = s_z = -\Delta w_c + h_c \theta_x \quad (16)$$

where $\omega_p = \omega^a(h^a - c_y^a, z_p) - \omega^a(-h^b - c_y^b, z_p)$, $h = h^a + h^b$ and $h_c = h^a + h^b + c_y^b - c_y^a$.

If lateral slip is ignored ($s_z = 0$), additional constraints can be formulated as follows:

$$\Delta w_c = h_c \theta_x \quad (17)$$

which gives:

$$w_c^b = w_c^a + h_c \theta_x \quad (18)$$

and

$$\theta_y^b = \theta_y^a - h_c \theta_{x,x} \quad (19)$$

2.4 Strain field

Using the developed beam kinematics in Eqs. (12), (13) and (14), the first order approximation of the Green-Lagrange strain can be expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_x^k = u_{0,x}^k - y^k \theta_{z,x}^k + z^k \theta_{y,x}^k + \omega^k \theta_{x,xx}^k \quad (20)$$

$$\gamma_{xy}^k = \left(\frac{\partial \omega^k}{\partial y} - z^k \right) \theta_{x,x}^k \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_{xz}^k = \left(\frac{\partial \omega^k}{\partial z} + y^k - c_y^k \right) \theta_{x,x}^k \quad (22)$$

3 EQUILIBRIUM CONDITION

The equilibrium condition of the composite beam possessing a single row of connectors is derived on the basis of the virtual work principle. Using the displacement fields developed in Eqs. (12), (13) and (14), we can express the balance between the work done by external and internal forces for an arbitrary virtual displacement. The beam is supposed to be subjected to external loading consisting of concentrated forces and moments $\mathbf{Q}_n$. Thus, the virtual work principle for the composite beam can be formulated as:

$$\sum_{k=a,b} \int_{V^k} \left(\sigma_x^k \delta \varepsilon_x^k + \tau_{xy}^k \delta \gamma_{xy}^k + \tau_{xz}^k \delta \gamma_{xz}^k \right) dV^k + \int_0^L \mathbf{D}_{sc}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{sc} dx = \delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{Q}_n \quad (23)$$

- σ_x^k , τ_{xy}^k and τ_{xz}^k are the axial and the shear stresses acting on the beam (k) cross-section;
- $\delta \varepsilon_x^k$, $\delta \gamma_{xy}^k$ and $\delta \gamma_{xz}^k$ are, respectively their corresponding virtual strains;
- $\mathbf{D}_{sc}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{sc}$ is the virtual work done by the shear forces in the connection at the interface
i.e.: $\mathbf{D}_{sc}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{sc} = D_{px}^{sc} \delta s_{px} + D_z^{sc} \delta s_z$
- $\mathbf{q}$ is the nodal displacements of the composite beam element given by:

$$\mathbf{q} = \left[\mathbf{q}_0^T \quad \mathbf{q}_m^T \quad \mathbf{q}_L^T \right]^T$$

with

$$\mathbf{q}_0 = \left[u_0^{a,i} \quad u_0^{b,i} \quad v_c^i \quad w_c^{a,i} \quad w_c^{b,i} \quad \theta_x^i \quad \theta_y^{a,i} \quad \theta_y^{b,i} \quad \theta_z^i \quad \theta_{x,x}^i \right]^T; \quad \mathbf{q}_m = \left[u_0^{a,m} \quad u_0^{b,m} \right]^T \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_L = \left[u_0^{a,j} \quad u_0^{b,j} \quad v_c^j \quad w_c^{a,j} \quad w_c^{b,j} \quad \theta_x^j \quad \theta_y^{a,j} \quad \theta_y^{b,j} \quad \theta_z^j \quad \theta_{x,x}^j \right]^T$$

$\mathbf{q}_m$ represents the considered additional degrees of freedom associated with the axial displacements of the two beam layers (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The composite beam's degrees of freedom

4 CONSTITUTIVE LAW

For linear and isotropic material, the axial and shear stresses of the beam can be related to the first-order Green-Lagrange strain as:

$$\sigma_x^k = E^k \varepsilon_x^k \quad (25)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^k = G^k \gamma_{xy}^k \quad (26)$$

$$\tau_{xz}^k = G^k \gamma_{xz}^k \quad (27)$$

Where E^k and G^k are the young and shear modulus of the beam (k), respectively. K_{px} and K_z represent, respectively, the uniformly distributed connection stiffness for axial and lateral slip of connector row (p). By considering a linear behaviour for the inter-layer connection, the contact forces and slip can be related as follows:

$$D_{px}^{sc} = K_{px} S_{px} \quad (28)$$

$$D_z^{sc} = K_z S_z \quad (29)$$

5 DISPLACEMENT BASED FORMULATION

In this section, we derive the standard stiffness matrix of the composite beam element based on selected shape functions that approximate the element's displacement fields. To accomplish this, we adopt Hermite interpolation functions for vertical and lateral displacements, as well as for the twisting angle, while using quadratic polynomials for axial displacements.

By combining the definitions of the strain fields in Eqs. (12), (13) and (14) with the constitutive laws of Eqs. (25), (26), (27), (28) and (29), the principle of virtual work can be formulated as follows:

$$\int_0^L (\tilde{\delta} \delta \mathbf{d})^T \mathbf{K}_m (\tilde{\delta} \mathbf{d}) dx + \int_0^L (\tilde{\delta}_{sc} \delta \mathbf{d})^T \mathbf{K}_{sc} (\tilde{\delta}_{sc} \mathbf{d}) dx = \delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{Q}_n \quad (30)$$

where:

$$\tilde{\delta} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2 x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2 x} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2 x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2 x} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad \tilde{\delta}_{sc} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \\ -h \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 \\ 0 & h_c \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{d} = [u_0^a \quad u_0^b \quad v_c \quad w_c^a \quad w_c^b \quad \theta_x]^T \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_m = \begin{bmatrix} E^a A^a & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E^a A^a & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \overline{EI}_z^s & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & E^a I_y^a & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & E^b I_y^b & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \overline{GJ}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \overline{EI}_\omega^s \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{K}_{sc} = \begin{bmatrix} K_x & 0 \\ 0 & K_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} I_y^k &= \int_{A^k} (z^k)^2 dA; & I_z^k &= \int_{A^k} (y^k)^2 dA; & I_x^k &= \int_{A^k} [(y^k)^2 + (z^k)^2] dA; & I_\omega^k &= \int_{A^k} (\omega^k)^2 dA; \\ C_t^k &= \int_{A^k} [z^k \omega_{,y}^k - (y^k - c_y^k) \omega_{,z}^k] dA; & J^k &= I_x^k + (c_y^k)^2 A^k - C_t^k; & \overline{EI}_z^s &= E^a I_z^a + E^b I_z^b; \\ \overline{GJ}^s &= G^a J^a + G^b J^b; & \overline{EI}_\omega^s &= E^a I_\omega^a + E^b I_\omega^b; & \overline{EA} &= \frac{E^a A^a E^b A^b}{E^a A^a + E^b A^b}. \end{aligned}$$

By introducing the definition of the shape functions into Eq. (30), the weak form of the virtual work principle can be expressed as follows:

$$\delta \mathbf{q}^T \left[\int_0^L (\tilde{\partial} \mathbf{N})^T \mathbf{K}_m (\tilde{\partial} \mathbf{N}) dx + \int_0^L (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \mathbf{N})^T \mathbf{K}_{sc} (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \mathbf{N}) dx \right] \mathbf{q} = \delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{Q}_n \quad (34)$$

where $\mathbf{N}$ is the matrix of the considered shape functions, which satisfies: $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{q}$.

Consequently, the stiffness matrix of the composite element can be evaluated as:

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \int_0^L (\tilde{\partial} \mathbf{N})^T \mathbf{K}_m (\tilde{\partial} \mathbf{N}) dx + \int_0^L (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \mathbf{N})^T \mathbf{K}_{sc} (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \mathbf{N}) dx \quad (35)$$

When using high lateral connection stiffness, the lateral slip is often ignored and the lateral deformation of the two beam layers is found to be dependent (Eqs. (17), (18) and (19)). Therefore, the system of degrees of freedom (DOFs) is reduced from 22 (Eq. (24)) to only 18 DOFs. Thus, the new system of DOFs $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} &= [\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_0^T \quad \mathbf{q}_m^T \quad \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_L^T]^T \\ \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_0 &= [u_0^{a,i} \quad u_0^{b,i} \quad v_c^i \quad w_c^{a,i} \quad \theta_x^i \quad \theta_y^{a,i} \quad \theta_z^i \quad \theta_{x,x}^i]^T; \quad \mathbf{q}_m = [u_0^{a,m} \quad u_0^{b,m}]^T \\ \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_L &= [u_0^{a,j} \quad u_0^{b,j} \quad v_c^j \quad w_c^{a,j} \quad \theta_x^j \quad \theta_y^{a,j} \quad \theta_z^j \quad \theta_{x,x}^j]^T \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Consequently, the expression of the composite stiffness matrix can be readjusted as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_e = \int_0^L (\tilde{\partial} \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \tilde{\mathbf{N}})^T \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m (\tilde{\partial} \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \tilde{\mathbf{N}}) dx + \int_0^L (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \tilde{\mathbf{N}})^T \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{sc} (\tilde{\partial}_{sc} \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \tilde{\mathbf{N}}) dx \quad (37)$$

where:

$$\tilde{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & h_c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{sc} = [K_x]; \begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m(i, j) = \mathbf{K}_m(i, j); (i, j) \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7\} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m(6, 6) = \overline{GJ}^s + G^b A^b h_c^2 \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

and $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}$ is the reduced matrix of shape functions, which satisfies: $\mathbf{d} = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}\tilde{\mathbf{N}}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$.

6 THE CROSS-SECTIONAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITE SECTION

To derive the cross-sectional properties of the composite section, we will use the definition of the composite stiffness matrix in Eq. (35). The core concept of the methodology is to adopt a single-beam analogy when determining the composite beam rigidities. By considering that the additional two DOFs $\mathbf{q}_m$ does not transfer external loading, we can eliminate them through a condensation process of the element stiffness matrix. By definition, the diagonals of the element stiffness matrix represent the beam rigidities associated with the beam's respective DOFs. Using the definition of the condensed element stiffness matrix, the ten first rigidities can be expressed as follows:

$$K(u_0^{a,i}, u_0^{a,i}) = \frac{E^a A^a}{L} + \frac{10\overline{EA}}{3\left(10\frac{\overline{EA}}{K_x L^2} + 1\right)L} + \frac{K_x L^2}{8\left(10\frac{\overline{EA}}{K_x L^2} + 1\right)L} \quad (39)$$

$$K(u_0^{b,i}, u_0^{b,i}) = \frac{E^b A^b}{L} + \frac{10\overline{EA}}{3\left(10\frac{\overline{EA}}{K_x L^2} + 1\right)L} + \frac{K_x L^2}{8\left(10\frac{\overline{EA}}{K_x L^2} + 1\right)L} \quad (40)$$

$$K(v_c^i, v_c^i) = \frac{12}{L^3} \left(\overline{EI}_z^s + \frac{h^2 \overline{EA}}{\frac{10\overline{EA}}{L^2 K_x} + 1} \right) \quad (41)$$

$$K(w_c^{a,i}, w_c^{a,i}) = \frac{12}{L^3} \left(E^a I_y^a + \frac{13}{420} K_z L^4 \right) \quad (42)$$

$$K(w_c^{b,i}, w_c^{b,i}) = \frac{12}{L^3} \left(E^b I_y^b + \frac{13}{420} K_z L^4 \right) \quad (43)$$

$$K(\theta_x^i, \theta_x^i) = \frac{6\overline{GJ}^s}{5L} + \frac{12\overline{EI}_\omega^s}{L^3} + \frac{13}{35} K_z h_c^2 L \quad (44)$$

$$K(\theta_y^{a,i}, \theta_y^{a,i}) = \frac{4E^a I_y^a}{L} + \frac{K_z L^3}{105} \quad (45)$$

$$K(\theta_y^{a,i}, \theta_y^{a,i}) = \frac{4E^a I_y^a}{L} + \frac{K_z L^3}{105} \quad (46)$$

$$K(\theta_y^{b,i}, \theta_y^{b,i}) = \frac{4E^b I_y^b}{L} + \frac{K_z L^3}{105} \quad (47)$$

$$K(\theta_z^i, \theta_z^i) = \frac{4\overline{EI}_z^s}{L} + \frac{4h^2\overline{EA}}{3\left(\frac{10\overline{EA}}{L^2K_x} + 1\right)L} + \frac{h^2L^2K_x}{8\left(\frac{10\overline{EA}}{L^2K_x} + 1\right)L} \quad (48)$$

$$K(\theta_{x,x}^i, \theta_{x,x}^i) = \frac{4\overline{EI}_\omega^s}{L} + \frac{2\overline{GJ}^s}{15}L + \frac{K_zL^3h_c^2}{105} \quad (49)$$

For a single beam under Vlasov theory considerations, the seven rigidities that corresponds to the seven DOFs can be evaluated as follows:

$$K(u_0^i, u_0^i) = \frac{EA}{L} \quad (50)$$

$$K(v_c^i, v_c^i) = \frac{12}{L^3}EI_z \quad (51)$$

$$K(w_c^i, w_c^i) = \frac{12}{L^3}EI_y \quad (52)$$

$$K(\theta_x^i, \theta_x^i) = \frac{6GJ}{5L} + \frac{12EI_\omega}{L^3} \quad (53)$$

$$K(\theta_y^i, \theta_y^i) = \frac{4EI_y}{L} \quad (54)$$

$$K(\theta_z^i, \theta_z^i) = \frac{4EI_z}{L} \quad (55)$$

$$K(\theta_{x,x}^i, \theta_{x,x}^i) = \frac{4EI_\omega}{L} + \frac{2GJ}{15}L \quad (56)$$

6.1 Effective bending stiffness around the z-z axis

Using the analogy between the *Eq. (41)* and *Eq. (51)*, the effective bending stiffness around the z-z axis can be evaluated as follows:

$$EI_z^{eff} = \overline{EI}_z^s + \frac{h^2\overline{EA}}{\frac{10\overline{EA}}{L^2K_x} + 1} \quad (57)$$

In reference (6), the authors proposed both an upper and a lower bound to the elastic effective bending stiffness as:

$$EI_{z,lower}^{eff} = \overline{EI}_z^s; \quad EI_{z,upper}^{eff} = \overline{EI}_z^s + h^2\overline{EA} \quad (58)$$

The formula presented in *Eq. (57)* is consistent with both bounds of the effective bending stiffness given in *Eq. (58)*:

$$EI_z^{eff}(K_x \cong 0) = EI_{z,lower}^{eff}; \quad EI_z^{eff}(K_x \cong \infty) = EI_{z,upper}^{eff} \quad (59)$$

6.2 Torsional and warping rigidity

Considering the analogy between the *Eq. (44)* and *Eq. (53)*, the effective torsional rigidity as well as the warping constant can be formulated as follows:

$$GJ^{eff} = \overline{GJ}^s + \frac{3}{7}K_zh_c^2L^2; \quad EI_\omega^{eff} = \overline{EI}_\omega^s - \frac{1}{84}K_zh_c^2L^4 \quad (60)$$

According to *Eq. (60)*, lateral slip negatively influences the warping constant, posing a limitation in the computation of EI_ω^{eff} for strong connection stiffness K_z . If lateral slip is omitted (*Eq. (37)*), the expressions of GJ^{eff} and EI_ω^{eff} become:

$$GJ^{eff} = \overline{GJ}^s + G^b A^b h_c^2; EI_\omega^{eff} = \overline{EI}_\omega^s + h_c^2 E^b I_y^b \quad (61)$$

Eq. (61) highlights the contribution of the existing lever arm between the shear centres of the two beams on the values of both GJ^{eff} and EI_ω^{eff} .

Referring to the Eq. (60) and Eq. (61), and depending on the value K_z , GJ^{eff} can be calculated as follows:

$$GJ^{eff} = \overline{GJ}^s + \frac{3}{7} K_z h_c^2 L^2; K_z \leq \frac{7G^b A^b}{3L^2} \quad (62)$$

$$GJ^{eff} = \overline{GJ}^s + G^b A^b h_c^2$$

7 EXAMPLES AND COMPARAISONS

7.1 Effective bending stiffness

In this section, we will assess the performance of the proposed expression in Eq. (57) in comparison to the gamma method outlined in Eurocode 5 (reference (7)). In the following, we will consider two rectangular cross-sections connected by a single line of connectors, as shown Fig. 3. The connection stiffness is equal to $K_x = 50 \text{ MPa}$.

Fig. 3. Two-layered composite section

Let's assume $h^a = 30 \text{ cm}$ and $h^b = k h^a$. The Table 1 compiles the values for EI_z^{eff} obtained for several values of k .

Table 1. Effective bending stiffness around z-z axis [N.m²]

k	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
Gamma (63)	5.0391e+07	5.2396e+07	5.7458e+07	6.7092e+07	8.2809e+07
Actual (57)	5.0383e+07	5.2385e+07	5.7444e+07	6.7073e+07	8.2786e+07
Relative error (%)	0.0161	0.0216	0.0259	0.0282	0.0283

Gamma method:

$$EI_z^{eff} = \overline{EI}_z^s + E^a A^a d^{a2} + \gamma_b E^b A^b d^{b2}$$

$$d^a = \frac{\gamma_b E^b A^b (h^a + h^b)}{E^a A^a + \gamma_b E^b A^b}; d^b = \frac{E^a A^a (h^a + h^b)}{E^a A^a + \gamma_b E^b A^b}; \gamma_b = \left(I + \frac{\pi^2 E^b A^b}{K_x L^2} \right)^{-1} \quad (63)$$

7.2 Effective torsional rigidity

To validate the performance of the proposed expression in Eq. (62), we consider an example from the literature. In reference (8), the authors investigated the structural response of a 2 m cantilever beam subjected to an eccentric point load at the tip of the upper beam layer (b).

The considered external load configuration can be summarized as follows:

$$M_x = 1.25 \text{ kN.m}; P_z = -10 \text{ kN}; P_y = -20 \text{ kN} \quad (64)$$

Table 2. Effective torsional rigidity [N.m²]

	(8)	Eq. (62)
GJ^{eff}	1.3889e+06	1.3704e+06

Based on the results of Table 2, Eq. (62) provides a good approximation to the torsional rigidity with only a 1.33 % relative error. The observed disparity in Table 2 can be attributed to the fact that the authors in reference (8) did not account for the influence of warping effects when developing their beam formulation.

8 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a new methodology for estimating the cross-sectional properties of a two-layered mono-symmetrical composite beam with a single line of connectors. A good agreement with the Eurocode 5's formula is observed for computing the effective bending stiffness. Additionally, the expressions for the torsional rigidity and the warping constant provide good estimation compared to an example from the literature. Further investigations are needed to account for the influence of connector position and explore possibilities for considering multiple lines of connections. In addition to that, it is necessary to incorporate the effect of the inter-layer connections on the warping of the composite section.

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